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ZERO WASTE FLIGHTS

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"A few minutes from now, we shall be landing at our destination airport. In preparation for our descent, your Cabin Crew will now collect all items for disposal. Kindly clear your seat pockets of any litter. Thank you for your cooperation."

This is the common announcement that passengers will hear in every flight before the landing procedures. After which, the cabin crew will go around to collect all disposables and check every seat to make sure that everything is in order. The Chief Pilot will then announce the descent procedures.

Have you ever wondered where these disposables and human wastes go to after every flight? Does every passenger know how much average trash he/she generates in every flight?

There has been significant attention on the carbon footprints generated by each flight, but this relatively small factor has often been overlooked by many passengers and airline companies.

In 2019, the International Air Transport Association (IATA) released the IATA Cabin Waste Handbook, aimed at establishing strategic drivers and identifying factors that could enhance resource efficiency. According to this handbook, the aviation industry generates an estimated 5.6 million tons, or approximately 5.7 billion kilograms, of passenger waste annually. This translates to an average of 1.4 kilograms per person per flight (WRAP, 2019). Given the sustained economic and tourism growth in various regions worldwide, this figure is likely to increase unless there are significant changes, particularly in terms of policies and procedures implemented by civil aviation authorities and airline management.

Many airlines lack recycling programs for passenger waste, resulting in both organic and inorganic trash being compacted in landfills. This process leads to the accumulation of tons of undecomposed waste. If left unaddressed, this issue could potentially escalate into a significant problem for both the government and the community in the future.

But why do the airlines use plastics and other disposable materials in flight?

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Indeed, the consideration of the weight of materials onboard every aircraft plays a significant role. Some materials may be heavier than plastic, potentially adding extra weight to the aircraft. This consideration is part of a strategy employed by companies to enhance the fuel efficiency of their aircraft.

Moreover, the recycling of used materials is typically prohibited in the airline industry due to regulations set by respective civil aviation authorities. These regulations enforce stringent quarantine procedures aimed at controlling the contamination of foods and beverages from external elements.

With the persistent rise in non-recyclable waste, several airline companies and organizations have begun taking action to address societal concerns regarding waste reduction and to genuinely adhere to various rules and regulations.

For example, the European Union (EU) has launched the "Life + Zero Cabin Waste" initiative, with the goal of minimizing aircraft waste on every flight. This project specifically targets recoverable solid waste generated on Category 1 International flights as well as Category 3 EU flights. Additionally, the program's environmental impact will be assessed and monitored through the Cycle Assessment framework established by the EU (European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, 2019).

Another notable initiative was the program implemented by All-Nippon Airways (ANA), which introduced paper inflight meal containers in December 2022. This move by the ANA Group underscores its commitment to reducing plastic waste and aligns with the achievement of the United Nations' 17 Sustainable Development Goals, representing a significant step toward a long-term environmental solution (All-Nippon Airways, 2022).

In the Philippines, Cebu Pacific Air has launched a program aimed at promoting environmental protection and minimizing cabin waste by encouraging passengers to bring their own materials and eco bags, and to practice responsible waste disposal. Beginning October 1, 2018, Cebu Pacific transitioned from plastic utensils to bio-compostable ones made from polylactic acid, derived from renewable sources. The Juan Effect program invites all stakeholders to join forces, collaborate, and cooperate in concerted efforts to reduce cabin waste and promote sustainable waste management practices (Air Transport Action Group, 2018).

The Philippine Air Lines, the flag carrier of the Philippines, has transitioned from its previous "Take, Make, Waste" system to the "Return and Renew" program in response to growing demands for in-flight services. Revived by PAL's catering division, this initiative aims to replace single-use plastic materials with sustainable alternatives, aligning with broader conservation efforts and bolstering environmental protection measures (Philippine Air Lines, 2021).

As the world returns to the exciting setting of tourism, the aviation industry is steadily recovering from the setbacks caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. From the limited number of flights during the peak of the crisis, tourists can now revel in a maximized number of available flights per day, facilitating visits to desired attractions not only in the Philippines but also around the globe. However, this resurgence poses a risk of increased human and solid

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waste, potentially leading to improper disposal practices. It is imperative that every air passenger becomes mindful and considerate of the environment, viewing this as an opportunity to promote responsible waste management.

Every person in this world should take actions to promote responsible waste management. This problem is not only a call to the aviation industry but also for the passengers to cooperate in promoting sustainability and do their own part.

Waste is certainly evident, but achieving zero cabin waste is possible through genuine acts of kindness and an indisputable concern for the future, which involves actively contributing to the preservation of the environment.

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